

ANALYSIS OF CASTING QUALITY PARAMETERS OF GRAY CAST IRON UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF MODIFIERS

^aJamshidbek Khasanov DSc researcher (PhD), ^bDSc., prof Nodir Turakhodjaev,
^aAndijan State Technical Institute, Andijan, Uzbekistan
^bTashkent State Technical University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

One of the important tasks in the world today is to obtain high-quality, inexpensive thin-walled cast products based on increasing the strength, quality, mechanical and operational properties of parts used in the mechanical engineering and manufacturing industries obtained by casting. In addition, the need for lightweight products with high strength is increasing to reduce energy and fuel consumption. As a result of the increasing demand for thin-walled cast products in the world, many techniques and technologies have been developed, requiring the production of high-quality, inexpensive and competitive parts from them. For reference, in 2021, gray cast iron had the largest market share in the global steel and cast iron production market, accounting for 37% [1].

Table 1

The chemical composition of the samples obtained based on the results of the research

Sample	Mass number of elements %								
	C	Mn	Si	Cr	P	S	Ni	Cu	Mo
N – 1	3,30	0,69	2,14	0,11	0,074	0,064	0,06	0,10	0,3
N – 2	3,35	0,69	2,15	0,11	0,074	0,064	0,06	0,20	0,3
N – 3	3,32	0,65	2,20	0,11	0,074	0,064	0,06	0,50	0,3

Samples were cast into sand-clay molds based on Table 1 from the gray cast iron alloy obtained by fluidization in the DSP-0.5 furnace at the “Casting Mechanics Workshop” of Uzmetkombinat JSC and the furnaces of the laboratory of the “Foundry Technologies” department of Tashkent State Technical University.

Picture 1. Microstructures of copper phosphide 0.5% and molybdenum 0.3% in Carl Zeiss Ultra Plus Field Emission scanning electron microscope in the laboratory of "Iron and Steel" Institute of Karabuk University.

Separation of graphite from carbon is usually considered an important process in the production of details by liquefying cast iron, and is especially necessary in the

production of thin-walled products. It was observed that the ductility, strength and hardness of gray cast iron increased. When copper phosphide (CuP_2) is added to 0.8% or more, it was found in the course of research that, although its fluidity and hardness increased, its brittle property was high [2-5].

The technology of out-of-furnace processing of liquid alloy has been developed for obtaining thin-walled castings from gray cast iron. This makes it possible to increase the fluidity of the liquid alloy by 9–11%. During the cooling process of the casting, a scheme for placement of the lifting roof detail in the casting mold, which ensures uniform distribution of corrosion resistance on the strengthening surface, has been developed. This serves to select an effective mold material. The technology of in-furnace processing of liquid alloy has been developed for obtaining thin-walled castings from gray cast iron. This allows to increase the hardness of the cast product by 10–12%. In the gray cast iron liquefaction furnace, the casting technology has been developed, which provides increased efficiency after modification with the help of CuP_2 and Mo elements.

References

1. Kholmiraev, N., Turakhodjaev, N., Saidmakhamadov, N., Khasanov, J., Saidkhodjaeva, S., & Sadikova, N. (2023). Development of Technology of Making Shafts from Steel Alloy 35XGCL. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, 762 LNNS. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-40628-7_18
2. Khasanov J. et al. Development of technology for obtaining thin-walled details from gray cast iron in sand-clay moulds //International Journal of Mechatronics and Applied Mechanics. 2024. – No. 18. – P. 199–209.
3. Khasanov J, Turakhodjaev N, Fakhridin Makhmudov. “Improvement of Mold Material for Casting Thin-Walled Details from Gray Cast Iron” <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT> e-ISSN: 2615-8140 | p-ISSN: 2615-7071 Volume: 4 Issue: 12 | December 2022 © <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/3785>
4. Nodir, T., Nosir, S., Shirinkhon, T., Erkin, K., Azizakhon, T., & Mukhammadali, A. (2021). Development Of Technology To Increase Resistance Of High Chromium Cast Iron. The American Journal of Engineering and Technology, 3(03), 85-92
5. Saidmakhamadov N., Khasanov J., Rakhmanov R., Mirzajonov B. Cast iron liquefaction technology// Actual priorities of modern science, education and practice Proceedings of the XII International Scientific and Practical Conference Paris, France March 29 – April 01, 2022. – p. 812 – 817.